

hatch 7 days after being laid. The nymphs were kept on the plant for acquisition access and virus incubation. Seventeen days after egg laying, about 250 nymphs collected with an aspirator connected to a water stream sucker were used to inoculate 50 seedlings of each variety at the first- or second-leaf stage in a glass dish covered with a plastic cylinder. A screen sack with a small hole at one corner was on one side of each cylinder. After 1 day of inoculation, a pipe connected to a compressor was inserted into the hole. The nymphs were forced by air stream through the pipe to the corner of the screen sack and the plastic cylinder with the nymphs was transferred to a glass dish with fresh

seedlings of the other variety. Each group of nymphs was transferred to fresh seedlings several times and then killed (see figure).

The inoculated seedlings were grown in a greenhouse. The number of infected plants and their symptoms were recorded 1 month after inoculation. Five seedlings showing typical symptoms were selected and transplanted in a concrete tub. After heading, late symptoms were recorded.

An average of about 500 (range, 400–700) nymphs were obtained from 25 females/day of egg laying. If the nymph population was much greater than 500/plant, the plant often died before it could be used for inoculation.

The use of five diseased plants/week for egg laying gave about 2,500 viruliferous nymphs/week. If 250 insects were used to inoculate one variety and they were transferred four times/week, then 10 varieties/day or 40 varieties/week could be inoculated.

The following weekly schedule is suggested.

Friday – Allow 25 female BPH to lay eggs on a diseased plant.

Saturday – Kill all female insects.

Monday – Collect nymphs and divide them into groups of 250 each.

Monday-Friday – Inoculate daily by transfer.

Friday – Kill the nymphs. ■

Differential host reactions to blast

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Cooperative screening of the International Rice Blast Nursery (IRBN) from 1975 to 1979 by rice scientists in different countries has led to the identification of several good resistant donor varieties, both traditional and improved, and differential host reactions to the blast pathogen at different locations. Most of

the resistant semidwarf breeding lines were selections from crosses involving the tall donors Tetep, Carreon, Tadukan, Dawn, Sigadis, and Pankhari 203, either singly or in combinations. Those lines (some samples are IR1905-PP1 1-29-4-61, IR3259-8-172-5, IR4547-2-1-2, IR9852-18-1) showed resistance at more than 75% of 50 test sites in Asia, Africa, and Latin America.

Key locations for identifying differential reactions were identified, based on the level of disease pressure and consistency of varietal reactions over

time – Parwanipur, Nepal; Lampegon, Indonesia; and Bumbong Lima, Malaysia. The information from these locations combined with reactions at other specified locations indicated 8 major groups and 15 varieties distinctive in host-response patterns. The varieties could serve as useful differentials in future research on blast disease (see table). B40, Fanny, and Kung-shan-wu-shan-ken can serve as susceptible checks at all or most locations. Tetep and Carreon exhibited resistance reactions at almost all locations. ■

Blast differentials based on International Rice Blast Nursery (IRBN) results, 1975–79.

Group	Cultivar	Reaction ^a						
		Major groups			Within group distinction			
		Parwanipur, Nepal	Lampegon, Indonesia	Bumbong Lima, Malaysia	IRRI, Philippines	Bac Ha, Vietnam	Cali, Colombia	Peradeniya, Sri Lanka
1	242/105	R	R	S				
2	IR1529-680-3	R	S	R	S		S	
	IR2071-176-2	R	S	R	R		R	
3	B25	R	S	S	R	R	R	
	CI 8985	R	S	S	S	S	S	
	BG94-1	R	S	S	R	R	S	
	CO25	R	S	S	S	R	R	
4	B46	S	R	R		S		
	Zenith	S	R	R		MR		
5	Chokoto	S	R	S				R
	CI 5309	S	R	S				S
6	B50	S	S	R		R		
	T23	S	S	R		S		
7	Tetep	R	R	R				
8	Fanny	S	S	S				

^aR = resistant, S = susceptible, MR = moderately resistant.